

RESEARCH ARTICLE

In Depth Battery Aging Analysis: A Key to Sustainable Energy Storage in Microgrids

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ABSTRACT The increasing use of renewable energy makes balancing generation and demand in power systems more challenging. This has led to a growing focus on battery technologies and energy storage solutions. These systems are essential for the effective integration of renewable energy into sustainable power networks. However, most experimental studies of lithium-ion batteries are limited to deep charge and discharge cycles, which do not fully represent how batteries operate in stationary applications. In these applications, batteries experience not only the main charge and discharge processes but also additional stress from current fluctuations due to the variable nature of renewable energy. These smaller cycles, known as micro-cycles, have a depth of discharge of less than 2% and occur alongside the primary charge and discharge processes. This paper presents the results of an experimental study focused on battery aging, considering micro-cycles that emulate real-world conditions for batteries in microgrid storage systems. It demonstrates that the degradation in storage systems occurs differently when compared to deep charge and discharge cycles. It provides a detailed analysis of the degradation processes occurring in microgrid batteries using EIS diagnostics and post-mortem analysis and demonstrates the applicability of the findings for renewable energy systems.

INDEX TERMS Battery degradation, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, energy storage, lithium-ion battery, microgrid, renewable energy.

I. INTRODUCTION

The electrification of the automotive transport sector and the transition to sustainable energy are two of the most significant challenges facing modern society [1]. One approach to address these challenges is by implementing microgrids, which provide a platform for integrating renewable distributed generation. By incorporating energy storage systems and flexible loads, microgrids create a localized, small-scale

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power system that offers numerous advantages, such as enhanced operational flexibility, improved system reliability, and cost-efficient operation [2]. As the demand for integrating higher levels of renewable energy grows and the need to reduce the costs of meeting peak demand intensifies, energy storage technologies have gained increasing attention [3]. These systems enable the shifting of energy from peak-demand periods to off-peak times and the storage of excess renewable energy for later use, supplying it back to the grid when needed. Additionally, their fast-ramping capabilities make energy storage a highly competitive resource

for addressing the variability and uncertainty that come with renewable energy generation [4], [43]. For energy storage purposes, lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries are used due to their high energy density and long cycle life [5].

Taking into account that the cost of the battery is one of the key parameters affecting the overall cost of a microgrid [6], and considering that the approach used for the battery degradation model has been proven to have a significant effect on the sizing and energy management of Li-ion batteries [7], the analysis of battery aging should be done with the due attention. However, batteries are often treated as black boxes, and the impact of operating conditions on their lifespan is not given sufficient consideration [2], [4], [8], [9], [10], [11]. In response to this, Wang et al. proposed a new approach to energy storage management [2], estimating battery degradation by means of a formula from 1997 that was empirically derived for NiCd batteries. Li et al. [4] estimate the economic savings of an energy system with battery storage, with the lifespan of the system determined solely based on achievable Equivalent Full Cycles (EFC) and the manufacturer's datasheet. An EFC corresponds to the number of times the charge throughput of the cell amounts to twice its nominal capacity C_n , as given in (1):

$$EFC = \frac{\int_0^t |i_{cell}(\tau)| d\tau}{2C_n} \quad (1)$$

Similarly, Bandyopadhyay et al. [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17] used an empirical battery degradation model originally validated for electric vehicles, which only considers deep charge and discharge cycles.

The lifetime of a Li-ion battery is known to depend on variables such as the number of cycles, operating temperature, voltage and current. Therefore, various experimental studies have been published to study these effects. However, in the real operation of stationary energy storage systems, short-term reverse current throughput occurs [18], [19]. These fluctuations during charging or discharging that do not exceed 2% of State of Charge (SOC) can be defined as micro-cycles. Based on research by Li et al. [20] who present that battery lifetime decreases with increasing current throughput, micro-cycles could be expected to accelerate the State of Health (SOH) reduction during the use of a battery. In contrast, Vazini et al. [21] present the positive effect of short pulses, where with sinusoidal ripple current charging, the battery reached an 80% SOC 10% faster than with conventional CC-CV charging. Additionally, the temperature during the sinusoidal charging process was approximately 0.5 °C lower. Furthermore, ripple charging has been reported to reduce ohmic losses by 52% compared to CC-CV charging [22]. This variability found in different research approaches is proof of the pertinence of experimental studies focused on understanding the effect of micro-cycles in the lifetime of Li-ion batteries. Some authors propose non-destructive measurement techniques to study the effect of micro-cycles in the electrical characteristics of a battery. In this sense, studies of capacity

evolution or impedance evolution by means of impedance spectroscopy are proposed. Other authors, however, focus on the material analysis, studying the effect of micro-cycles on the active materials of a cell. This topic is addressed by Ming Wang et al. [23], who present the effect of current pulses on Solid Electrolyte Interface (SEI) formation. They suggest that the charging type also affects the composition and structure of the SEI layer, which could directly impact the overall battery lifespan. This was also investigated in the study [17], which reveals distinct processes occurring during the third stage of lithiation at the anode under pulsed versus constant charging. In the case of constant charging, the anode may experience increased mechanical stress. These two approaches to the study of micro-cycles provide complementary information. However, comprehensive experimental studies analyzing the relationship between electrical characteristics and material degradation in a micro-cycle scenario have not been found in the literature. This paper covers this gap by means of a comprehensive analysis of capacity, impedance and material degradation due to micro-cycles. It is built on two previous contributions, the first one focused on the capacity analysis [3] and the second on impedance evolution [1]. In this paper, the main results of the previous contributions are compiled and complemented with a post-mortem analysis to assess the reasons for the electrical characteristics measured.

The main contribution of this work is the EIS analysis of the cells, which is linked with post-mortem analysis of the anode and cathode of the cell, based on Laser Scanning Microscopy. Results demonstrate that micro-cycles lead to up to four times slower growth of the SEI layer, thereby slowing down battery degradation. The potential applicability of these conclusions in the design and operation of energy storages is then presented.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. BATTERY USAGE PROFILES IN RENEWABLE ENERGY APPLICATIONS

To properly study the degradation processes in batteries used within microgrids, it is essential to understand the real-world loading profiles that the battery storage system experiences during operation. The aging experiments presented in this paper are designed to reflect typical battery operation profiles in renewable energy systems. The real operation of a 3.3 kWh Li-ion battery installed in a self-consumption system in northern Spain (42°48' 00.6"N 1°38' 04.4"W) was

TABLE 1. Micro-cycle test matrix.

	Depth of micro-cycle	Frequency (mHz)	Duty cycle
Continuous deep charge – discharge cycles with a current of 3 A (1C)	0%	-	-
Deep charge – discharge with superimposed micro-cycles	0.5%	11	25%
Deep charge – discharge with superimposed micro-cycles	1%	5.5	25%
Deep charge – discharge with superimposed micro-cycles	2%	2.75	25%

FIGURE 1. Number of cycles per DOD obtained for a self-consumption installation during 52 weeks of operation [1].

monitored over a 52-week period, and the data collected were subsequently analyzed using the Rainflow algorithm to serve as input for the aging experiments [18].

The number of cycles per Depth of Discharge (DOD) obtained for a self-consumption installation over 52 weeks of operation are illustrated in Figure 1. A noticeable number of micro-cycles (DOD < 2%) were recorded during the year. More than 30,000 cycles with DOD < 0.5% occurred. However, there were only 285 deep cycles with DOD > 80%, as discussed in detail in [5]. Given the substantial number of micro-cycles, it is crucial to properly assess their impact on the aging of Li-ion batteries. Consequently, a test matrix was developed, incorporating the effect of the most recurrent micro-cycles.

B. EXPERIMENTAL AGING OF LI-ION BATTERIES WITH MICRO-CYCLES

In general, battery aging can be described by (2), which incorporates both calendar and cycling-related degradation mechanisms [25]:

$$\Delta SOH_{(t=x)} = SF_T * SF_{DOD} * SF_C * R_{cal} \left(\frac{\Delta SOH}{dt} \right) * dt, \tag{2}$$

Here SF_T is the stress factor reflecting the influence of temperature, SF_{DOD} is the stress factor reflecting the influence of depth of discharge and SF_C reflects C-rate. Parameter R_{cal} reflects calendric ageing.

To eliminate all parameters except the cycling profile, C-rate was identical for cells and all experiments were performed in the Laboratory for Energy Storage and Microgrids at the Public University of Navarra in an Ineltec -30/300 thermal chamber at a controlled temperature of 20 °C ± 0.5 °C. A Neware BTS4016-5V battery tester was used for testing. The data were obtained via a four-terminal sensing method and the cell temperature was constantly monitored.

The tested batteries in this work were LG 18650 Li-ion cells with a nominal capacity of 3 Ah. According to the manufacturer’s information, each cell consists of a graphite + SiO2 anode and H-NMC cathode. The nominal cell voltage of the selected cell is 3.6 V, and the operating voltage range is from 2.5 V to 4.2 V.

A total of eight cells in four different scenarios were used for the experiment. Three scenarios included deep cycles superimposed with micro-cycling of different DODs. One scenario consisted of only deep cycles and was used as a baseline. The test matrix is shown in Table 1.

Figure 2 shows the aging profiles, in which the micro-cycles with DOD of 0.5% (red), 1% (blue) and 2% (green) are superimposed to a deep cycle. The DOD of the deep cycles shown in the figure is 80% (in terms of nominal capacity), which is limited by the reaching of the maximum cell voltage during the last part of the charge. All experiments are done at the same current amplitude 3A for main process and micro-cycles, which is 1C C-rate. The time between micro-cycles is adjusted, so that the batteries with micro-cycles of 0.5%, 1% and 2% complete a full cycle at the same time. In this work, the SOH is defined in (3), and the end of life (EOL) criteria is set as SOH < 70% based on [26].

$$SOH = 100 \cdot \frac{C}{C_i}, \tag{3}$$

C being the current charge capacity and C_i the initial capacity.

C. REFERENCE PERFORMANCE TESTS

Reference Performance Tests (RPT) are periodically performed every 20 cycles to monitor the cells’ degradation. To minimize their influence on the aging process, the following RPT procedure is applied:

1. Discharge the cell to its minimum voltage at a current of 1 A (C/3).

FIGURE 2. Aging profiles of the cells.

FIGURE 3. Impedance plot of a NMC battery cell.

2. Charge the cell to its maximum voltage at 1 A ($C/3$), followed by a constant-voltage stage until the current drops to 0.12 A ($C/25$).
3. Discharge the cell again at 1 A ($C/3$) to the minimum voltage.
4. Charge the cell using galvanostatic pulses with increments of $\Delta SOC = 20\%$ (0.6 Ah for pristine cell), at a current of 1 A.
5. Allow the cell to rest for 1 hour after each galvanostatic charge pulse.
6. Discharge the cell to $SOC = 50\%$ at a current of 1 A ($C/3$) and let it rest for 1 hour.
7. Perform an EIS: amplitudes between 50 mA for low frequencies and 500 mA for high frequency. This leads to voltage responses ranging from 2 mV (low frequency) to 10 mV (medium and high frequency). This range was selected to ensure system linearity and was confirmed to be consistent with the Kramers–Kronig relations.

D. ELECTROCHEMICAL IMPEDANCE SPECTROSCOPY METHOD

The EIS method was used in this work to provide a deeper analysis of battery cells’ materials and mechanisms in a non-destructive manner. During EIS measurements, a small AC signal over a wide frequency range is applied to the battery, and the cell response is measured [27]. Different components and processes within a cell operate on different timescales. Therefore, they have different time constants and can be separated in the frequency domain using this method. Given the inherently non-linear nature of electrochemical cells, it is essential to carefully control the applied current during impedance measurements to ensure that the cell operates within a pseudo-linear regime [28].

The most significant advantage of EIS is its measurement time, which is much shorter related to, for example, capacity testing. Another significant advantage is that it allows the possibility to separately analyze the chemical processes inside the battery [12].

FIGURE 4. Impedance plot of a NMC battery cell.

Figure 3 illustrates the relationship between the different parts of EIS chart and the chemical processes within the battery. This makes it possible to examine the different processes in parallel and so better determine what is happening inside the battery under the different aging profiles.

As shown in Figure 3, each part of the graph is linked to one of the chemical processes taking place inside the battery [29], [30]. More specifically, these processes can be quantified using an Equivalent Electrical Circuit (EEC), where each process is linked to an element of the EEC [31]. The selected EEC, based on work of Sihvo et al. [32], consists of serial resistance R_s , serial inductance L_s , and three components composed of constant phase element (CPE) and resistance R_x in parallel. The total impedance Z of the battery cell, based on the proposed equivalent circuit, is calculated as follows:

$$Z(\omega) = R_s + j\omega L_s + Z_1 + Z_2 + Z_3, \tag{4}$$

where

$$Z_k = \left(\frac{1}{\frac{1}{R_k} + \frac{1}{Z_{CPEk}}} \right), \quad k = 1, 2, 3. \tag{5}$$

Here R is resistance, L is the wiring inductance, j is the imaginary unit and ω is angular frequency. CPE is defined as [33]:

$$Z_{CPE} = \frac{1}{Q(j\omega)^N}. \tag{6}$$

Here, j is the imaginary unit, Q is the pre-factor of the CPE, and N is its exponent. Q parameter describes the position in the Nyquist graph relative to the y-axis and is the generalized capacitance, the N parameter represents how much the semicircle is deformed from the ideal semicircle in terms

TABLE 2. EEC parameters description.

EEC part	EEC parameter description – physical meaning
R_s	ohmic resistance of the cell
L_s	parasitic inductance and inductance of supply cables
$R_1 CPE_1$	parameters related to the impedance at frequencies of about 1 Hz - 100 Hz and to the processes taking place in the SEI layer
$R_2 CPE_2$	charge transfer of the electrochemical reaction
$R_3 CPE_3$	parameters related to diffusion in battery

of Nyquist plot. The meaning of each parameter is given in Table 2.

The chosen equivalent electrical circuit is shown in Figure 4. The fitting algorithm was created using Matlab software, using toolbox Zfit [34]. In all cases, the root mean square error of the fit did not exceed 2%, with an average fitting error of 0.96%.

E. POST-MORTEM ANALYSIS

The post-mortem analysis was carried out at the Electrical Energy Storage Technology group laboratories in TU Berlin. To do the post-mortem analysis, the cells were discharged to their end-of-discharge (EOD) voltage at a current of 0.1 C. Then, they were opened in a glovebox under an argon atmosphere (glovebox type MBRAUN UNILab pro, O2 and H2O concentration < 1 ppm). A Keyence VK-X200 series laser microscope, which was placed inside the same glovebox, was used to perform Laser Scanning Microscopy (LSM) of the samples extracted from the anodes and cathodes of the cells.

The Keyence VK-X200 microscope combines an optical image with a high-resolution laser image to provide a highly augmented image with high resolution, including a better visual result by means of the optical lens. This kind of image shows the evolution of the pore structure during the lifetime of the cells that undergo full cycles and allows its comparison with cells with a cycling profile that also includes micro-cycles. Conversely, the LSM images provide an accurate measurement of the surface thickness, allowing the analysis of the SEI layer distribution, lithium plating, as well as dendrite formation.

Post-mortem analysis was conducted on six cells, comparable results for four cells of different ages and aging profiles are presented below. The first one was a pristine cell, in which the original characteristics of the electrodes after manufacturing can be observed. The second cell was almost pristine, but it had undergone 20 full charge-discharge

FIGURE 5. Evolution of the SOH in cells subjected to different ageing scenarios.

FIGURE 6. EEC parameters evolution based on EFC: a) Series resistance; b) series inductance; c) resistance related to SEI layer, e) and f) parameters of CPE related to SEI layer; d) resistance related to charge transfer region; g) and h) parameters of CPE related to charge transfer region.

cycles that ensured the formation of a stable SEI layer [35]. The third cell had an SOH of 68%, which was reached with full charge-discharge cycles with 2%-DOD micro-cycles superimposed, as described in row 4 of Table 1. Finally, the fourth cell had a SOH of 65%, similar to cell 3, but it reached this SOH solely by means of full charge-discharge cycles, as described in row 1 of Table 1. This experimental design allows a comparative study of new cells, cells aged with micro-cycles, and cells aged without micro-cycles.

III. RESULTS

A. CAPACITY FADE: COMPARING AGEING WITH AND WITHOUT MICRO-CYCLES

As demonstrated in the work of A. Soto et al. [5], the aging processes with and without micro-cycles exhibit differing rates of degradation, as illustrated in Figure 5. Analyzing the number of achievable EFCs in terms of Ah throughput in the case with micro-cycles reveals that it is possible to attain approximately one-third more equivalent full cycles compared to the scenario without micro-cycles, before the battery reaches its end of life, defined as 70% of its nominal capacity.

FIGURE 7. Optical image and LSM height map of anode.

Based on these results, the experimental data were subjected to a more detailed analysis using EIS and microscopic images.

B. ELECTROCHEMICAL IMPEDANCE SPECTROSCOPY DIAGNOSTICS

The main difference between cells subjected to micro-cycles and cells without micro-cycles are found in parameters R_1 and Q_1 , as shown in Figure 6. Specifically, a fourfold increase in R_1 resistance occurs 1000 EFCs earlier in batteries aged without micro-cycles, as shown in Figure 6c, and a more significant deviation of the traces of Q_1 for cells without micro-cycles is observed in Figure 6e.

The remaining impedance parameters show no significant difference between the various cycling profiles. These two parameters (R_1 and Q_1) are attributed to the growth of the SEI layer built between the anode and the electrolyte [1]. Given that the remaining parameters are homogeneous among cells, no relevant difference is expected in the electric conductivity of the electrodes and ionic conductivity of the electrolyte, modelled by R_s , or the charge transfer phenomena occurring in both electrodes, represented by Q_2 , N_2 , and R_2 .

C. POST-MORTEM ANALYSIS OF MICROSCOPIC IMAGES

The post-mortem study presented herein is designed to validate the above-mentioned conclusions extracted from the

non-destructive EIS analysis. To do so, the cells described in Section II-B are disassembled, and optical and LSM images of different parts of the anode and cathode are compiled.

1) ANODE ANALYSIS

Figure 7 shows the LSM (left) and height map (right) images of the studied anodes. The corresponding areal roughness parameters are the arithmetical mean height S_a , the maximum height S_z and the texture aspect ratio S_{tr} (The numerical values are provided in Appendix.). The S_{tr} measures the uniformity of the surface. Figure 7a shows a portion of the pristine cell anode. The optical microscope image shows a clear particle distribution of the anode, with particle diameters in the order of hundreds of nm. The SEI layer is thin, allowing a clear differentiation of anode particles. The result of the LSM analysis shows a more accurate representation of the anode height. The surface of the pristine anode is quite even, with a maximum difference between the deepest and the highest point of around $30 \mu\text{m}$. A comparison between the optical and LSM images shows that the darker areas of the optical result are the deepest regions of the anode particle structure. By contrast, the anode particles that are lighter in the optical image are the highest parts in the height map representation.

Figure 7b shows the results of the cell that has undergone 20 full charge – discharge cycles. The SEI formation process can be considered finished. Optical and LSM images show

FIGURE 8. Optical image and LSM height map of cathode.

very similar results to those described for the pristine cell. This similarity makes sense, given that the SEI layer is designed to be as thin and even as possible. The edges of individual particles are clearly distinguishable, indicating that only the necessary growth of the initial SEI layer has occurred to stabilize the anode, without hindering the free movement of ions. In contrast, in Figure 7c on the left, which shows the optical image of the anode from a cell subjected to micro-cycles, the individual anode particles are less distinguishable, with some almost merging into one. This is attributed to lithium plating, meaning lithium particles are depositing without participating in charging and discharging processes, leading to a decrease in capacity. However, the height map remains practically the same as in cells with 100% capacity. There is a small lighter area indicating a slightly more uneven anode surface, though it only represents a variation of a few tens of percent.

In Figure 7d, which is the post-mortem analysis of the cell cycled without micro-cycles, notable differences are immediately apparent in both the optical image and LSM result. In the optical image, the edges of individual particles are entirely unrecognizable, as they merge in the darker areas of the image, which are lower, while only tall protrusions, appearing lighter, are visible on the surface. The analysis of the LSM height map and resulting roughness parameters confirm the conclusions from the optical images, showing

that the anode height has increased by more than four times compared to the pristine cell. The surface inhomogeneity of the anode is also significantly greater, given by a heavily decreased S_{tr} value, which could accelerate further uneven degradation processes and, in extreme cases, lead to separator puncture and internal short circuits [36].

In these images, it is very clear that degradation phenomena with and without micro-cycles have a distinctly different effect on the SEI layer. While degradation with full cycle cycling produces a highly irregular lithium plating on the electrode surface, degradation with micro-cycles results in a much more homogeneous SEI growth. This can be attributed to the inversed polarization of the anode caused by the micro-cycles, which promotes ion diffusion within the anode, thus reducing metallic lithium plating. The lithium plated when the cell is cycled without micro-cycles prevents lithium-ion intercalation in plated anode areas, thereby increasing the current density of the remaining regions, which in turn accelerates the degradation of these areas and, consequently, the cell as a whole.

2) CATHODE ANALYSIS

The results obtained from optical microscopy and LSM height map analysis of the cathode are shown in Figure 8. Similar to the anode analysis, these images allow a

comparative analysis of the cathode surface at various aging stages. The LSM images have the same scale as those of Figure 7, while the height map vertical axis is 4 times smaller in Figure 8 due to the lower growth of the cathode surface during aging.

Figure 8.a) shows the cathode of the pristine cell, where individual particles are already less distinguishable at first glance. This is, however, an expected condition and one of the main reasons why LSM images alone are typically insufficient for post-mortem analysis [37]. From the height map analysis, even cathode surface can be observed, with a few small protrusions, likely resulting from imperfections in the manufacturing process.

Figure 8.b) on the left, showing the cathode after the initial cycling (the first 20 cycles), presents a similar optical image to that of the pristine cell, which is unsurprising given the low cycle count. The LSM height map reveals a slightly lower average cathode height, which could be due to, for example, the loss of active material from the cathode. However, these height differences are relatively insignificant and could just as well be attributed to the inhomogeneity of the cathode.

The optical image in Figure c) is similar to all previous analyses of the cathode, however, compared to the LSM height maps in Figure 8.a) and Figure 8.b), the cathode surface is significantly more uniform, which could indicate the formation of a cathode surface layer primarily due to electrolyte oxidation [37].

In Figure 8.d), showing the optical image, a small fibrous structure is notable, which could be associated with the phenomenon of transition metal dissolution. This process involves the dissolution of cathode metal, potentially leading to dendrite growth or migration to the anode, causing an increase in the SEI layer. This phenomenon may correspond to the small peaks observed in the height map image. Additionally, the non-homogeneous surface could result from impurities introduced during manufacturing or disassembly.

Cathode degradation phenomena are observed by a comparative analysis of the images shown in Figure 8. The pristine cell, as well as the cell with 20 charge – discharge cycles have similar distribution of the cathode particles (optical image), and similar roughness, visualized by the height map. The cathode of the cell aged with full cycles and micro-cycles (Figure 8c) also has an even distribution of the particles and surface, showing no significant sign of aging. Finally, the cathode of the cell cycled only with full cycles, shown in Figure 8d, shows a similar particle distribution, but in the height map, a significant particle deposition is appreciated. This deposition is not attributed to cathode aging, given that the remaining parts of the cathode show no sign of significant degradation.

IV. DISCUSSION

It is interesting to note that the micro-cycles of the experiments presented in this paper almost double the lifespan of the cells in terms of EFC. If the EOL criteria is set at 70% SOH, the lifetime of cells used without micro-cycles ranges

between 1400 and 1900 EFC, as shown in Figure 5. However, cells with superimposed micro-cycles last around 3500 EFC.

The differences in the profiles of EEC parameters extracted from EIS curves also correspond with this conclusion. The parameters R_1 and Q_1 show the most significant differences. While cells aged without micro-cycles exhibit a fourfold increase in R_1 at approximately 1500 EFC, for cells aged with micro-cycles, this increase occurs around EFC 3000, which completely aligns with the differences observed in capacity fade. A similar phenomenon is observable in Q_1 , where a tenfold increase in the Q_1 parameter occurs at 1500 EFC for cells without micro-cycles, whereas for cells with micro-cycles, this increase does not occur until around 2700 EFC.

As described in Section II-D., the parameters R_1 and Q_1 represent the growth of the SEI layer, which occurs on the anode. Therefore, when comparing the results of the EIS analysis with the post-mortem analysis of anodes, the exact same conclusion is reached: The SEI layer grows several times faster in cells aged without micro-cycles, as illustrated in height map Fig 7 d. and its comparison with the remaining analyzed cells in that figure.

These differences can be explained by the distinct lithiation process occurring under pulsed charging, as reported in [17]. In phases I and II of lithiation, there are typically no observable differences between constant current (CC) and pulsed current (PC) charging. However, in phase III, CC charging leads to the formation of a double G band in the Operando Raman spectra, indicating an uneven distribution of Li-ions in graphite. As reported in [38], this phenomenon can be mitigated by pulsed current.

If, however, CC charging results in uneven Li-ion distribution, there is a risk of excessive mechanical stress on the anode. Should cracking begin to occur, it may promote the formation of a non-uniform SEI layer, which in turn would accelerate the overall degradation of the battery.

Often, pulsed currents are investigated without reversing the polarisation [17], [39] or as part of dynamic load protocols [40]. In the work shown here, it is assumed that the tests shown in the publications are further enhanced, as the electromotive force is reversed, and thus, a portion of intercalated ions is extracted again from the particles. Huang et al. show a possible service life extension of over 80% through pulse currents compared to a constant current with the same average current level [39]. For this, they use a pulse frequency of 0.05 Hz. It has also been shown that increasing this frequency reduces the overall increase in service life [39]. In contrast, Guo et al. show that a very high frequency improves the uniform deposition of Lithium on the electrode [17]. Thus, over the battery's lifetime, there is a compromise between the uniformity on the electrode surface and the total charge the battery has to handle.

Li et al. and Zhang et al. go into more detail about the behaviour at the boundary layer of Lithium using Li-metal electrodes. Here, the lifetime can be increased by superimposing a pulse current, which results in a more uniform deposition of metallic lithium on the surface of the elec-

trode. Zhang et al. attribute this to the concentration gradients caused by the slow movement of Li-ions [41]. Here, slow reactions and ion movements lead to a local accumulation of electrons at elevated points on the electrode. This ultimately leads to the formation of dendrites at these points. Li et al. discuss the influence of an electric field caused by a change in the current rate, which impacts both the diffusion and deposition of Lithium [42]. Here, too, using a pulsed current reduces Lithium dendrite growth, reducing the tendency for irreversible plating at vulnerable points. As stated in this paper and compared to the results from [17], [39], and [42], also shows that an ideal ratio between activated pulse current and switched-off pulse is achieved. This suggests that it is the switching frequency rather than the DOD that is not decisive. It is demonstrated in this work that because of an increase in DOD and thus a reduction in repolarisation steps, capacity fading increases again despite the same total charge amount.

Although this study was conducted on a single cell chemistry (NMC cathode with a graphite–SiO₂ composite anode), our analysis suggests that micro-cycles primarily affect SEI layer growth, a phenomenon that is intrinsic to graphite-based anodes in general. Accordingly, we hypothesize that the observed trends are applicable to a broad range of current Li-ion batteries employing graphite-based anodes. In contrast, Li₄Ti₅O₁₂ (LTO) anodes operate at higher potentials, where electrolyte reduction and conventional SEI formation are largely suppressed, and the nature of the interphase differs substantially [14].

We therefore restrict the generality of our conclusions to non-LTO Li-ion chemistries and propose that micro-cycles may have a beneficial impact on battery lifetime wherever graphite-based anodes are used.

This opens the possibility for generalization, suggesting that the presence of micro-cycles may have a positive impact on the lifetime of lithium-ion batteries regardless of the chemistry, except for LTO.

Overall, the influence of micro-cycles on battery degradation is clearly evident, and their consideration may be beneficial in the operation of battery energy storage systems. One possible direction for implementing this knowledge is to incorporate micro-cycles into charging profiles, where feasible during operation. Another potential approach is to account for this knowledge in predictive control strategies for battery storage systems, thereby enabling an operational strategy that extends battery lifetime. Finally, the findings from the post-mortem analysis may also be applied in the design of battery cells themselves, particularly regarding materials and cell design.

In any case, it is necessary to bear in mind that the results presented here are derived from the real-world operation of a battery energy storage system, but only four specific scenarios were selected for more detailed investigation and presentation. Therefore, when applying the conclusions presented in this study, it will always be necessary to first determine

the operating conditions of the microgrid under consideration and appropriately adapt the findings of this study to those conditions.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, a detailed study of degradation processes occurring in Li-ion batteries aged under conditions typical for sustainable microgrids is presented (deep cycles with superimposed micro-cycles).

Firstly, the capacity results indicate that batteries subjected to micro-cycles reach 70% SOH approximately 2,000 Equivalent Full Cycles later than those subjected to conventional deep discharges and charges, resulting in a twofold increase in operational lifespan in terms of EFC.

Secondly, the non-destructive electrochemical impedance analysis points towards the anode SEI as the reason for the different degradation rate, given that the largest difference is found in parameters R_1 and Q_1 . The SEI layer growth, which includes lithium plating, is inferred to be the main contributor to this different aging evolution.

Finally, the post-mortem analysis, that requires the destruction of the cells, shows the most significant difference of the material aging in the anode surface, which is the region where the SEI is built. The enhanced performance observed with micro-cycles is attributed to reversed anode polarization, which promotes ion diffusion and suppresses lithium plating. In contrast, cycling without micro-cycles leads to lithium plating that hinders intercalation and increases local current density as well as overall cell degradation.

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that micro-cycles significantly affect the degradation process of Li-ion batteries, effectively extending cell lifespan in terms of EFC.

All in all, if this detailed knowledge of degradation processes is considered in the design and dimensioning of battery storage systems for microgrids, it can be expected that algorithms utilizing this knowledge will be gentler on battery performance within the storage system. This approach can improve the accuracy of life expectancy estimates and reduce the expected costs for sustainable energy systems.

APPENDIX AREAL ROUGHNESS PARAMETERS

TABLE 3. Areal roughness parameters - anode.

	S_a [μm]	S_z [μm]	S_r
SOH 100% - pristine cell	0.597	7.986	0.79
SOH 100% - 20 deep cycles	0.57	6.637	0.78
SOH 68% with micro-cycles	0.514	7.035	0.668
SOH 65% without micro-cycles	3.384	31.332	0.312

TABLE 4. Areal roughness parameters - cathode.

	S_a [μm]	S_z [μm]	S_r
SOH 100% - pristine cell	0.486	7.554	0.749
SOH 100% - 20 deep cycles	0.571	8.808	0.733
SOH 68% with micro-cycles	0.384	9.037	0.826
SOH 65% without micro-cycles	0.467	7.064	0.914

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